

Prioritization strategies for non-target screening in environmental samples by chromatography – High-resolution mass spectrometry: A tutorial

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ABSTRACT

Non-target screening (NTS) using chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), has become fundamental for detecting and prioritizing chemicals of emerging concern (CECs) in complex environmental matrices. The vast number of generated features (m/z , retention time, and intensity) necessitate effective prioritization strategies to identify environmentally and toxicologically relevant CECs. Since compound identification remains a major bottleneck in NTS, prioritization is critical to focus identification efforts where they matter most.

This tutorial presents seven prioritization strategies: (1) Target and suspect screening for identifying known or suspected compounds using reference libraries. (2) Data quality filtering to apply quality control measures to reduce noise and the number of false positives. (3) Chemistry-driven prioritization using HRMS data properties to prioritize specific compound classes (e.g., halogenated substances, transformation products). (4) Process-driven – using spatial, temporal, or process-based comparisons (pre- and post-technical processes) to identify key features. (5) Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) and Virtual Effect-Directed Analysis (vEDA) prioritization to link chemical features to biological effects. (6) Prediction-based prioritization such as quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR) and machine learning to estimate risk or concentration levels, and (7) Pixel- or tile-based analysis where the chromatographic image (2D data) is used to pin-point regions of interest or for comparison of larger sample sets.

By integrating these prioritization strategies, this tutorial provides a structured foundation to evaluate both identified and unidentified features, prioritize high-risk compounds, and advance environmental risk assessment and regulatory decision-making.

1. Introduction

Environmental pollution from anthropogenic chemicals, driven by increasing production and widespread use, poses a major threat to environmental and human health [1]. Accurately profiling chemicals of emerging concern (CECs) in complex environmental samples is essential to address this challenge. Target screening is the most widely used approach for monitoring known pollutants due to its high sensitivity, selectivity, and provision of quantitative data (compound concentrations) [2]. This method focuses on a predefined set of known compounds, relying on commercially available reference standards for identification and quantification [3]. Typically, target compounds are

selected based on legislative frameworks (e.g., Stockholm Convention and REACH), environmental occurrences, or high production volumes [4,5]. Priority is given to substances with known persistence, bioaccumulation, toxicity (e.g., endocrine disruptors), or high mobility potential [6]. While target screening is effective for routine monitoring and regulatory compliance, it is limited to compounds with available reference standards.

Non-target screening (NTS) addresses chemical-related adverse effects that target methods often missed [7]. Many cases of ecotoxicity in wastewater and unexplained disease patterns cannot be explained by known target compounds [8,9]. Unlike target screening, which covers only a small fraction of the chemical space, NTS aims to detect, identify,

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and track unknown and emerging contaminants, providing a much broader coverage. This makes NTS a strong tool for revealing overlooked CECs and providing valuable insights for better risk assessment and regulatory decisions.

Liquid chromatography (LC) with high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) is the most used analytical method for NTS of water samples due to its broad compound coverage, high separation efficiency, and strong identification capabilities. Combining LC–HRMS with complementary techniques such as ion chromatography (IC), supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC), and one and two-dimensional gas chromatography (GC and GC × GC) can significantly expand compound coverage, allowing the detection of more polar, ionic, and volatile compounds [10–12].

NTS workflows are designed to address specific research questions and consist of key steps such as experimental design, quality assurance/control, sample preparation, chromatographic separation, and mass spectrometric detection [13]. After data acquisition, preprocessing is important to detect features — defined by mass-to-charge ratio (m/z), retention time (RT) and intensity (peak area) — group related features, and remove unreliable data through blank subtraction, intensity thresholds, and replicate consistency checks. Despite preprocessing, often thousands of reliable features per sample remain [14].

Prioritization is essential to efficiently narrow down detected features to those that require further identification significantly improving the overall workflow. With the large number of detected features, prioritization helps to streamline key tasks such as identification, quantification, risk assessment, and source apportionment [15]. However, despite its importance, prioritization in NTS remains underexplored [13].

A major challenge in NTS is the time-intensive manual curation required for initial peak annotation and confident compound identification. This process relies on confirmatory evidence from reference standards and additional experimental evidence, making it laborious. As a result, only a small fraction of detected compounds is confidently identified within typical project timeframes [16].

Advancements in data preprocessing have accelerated handling of large sample sets, particularly in fields like metabolomics [17]. High-throughput computational systems can now detect and group features across samples, while investment in additional instrumentation can boost sample throughput nearly linearly. However, the identification stage remains the primary bottleneck, with manual curation and annotation still labor-intensive and prone to becoming overwhelming [18,19]. Challenges such as isobaric compounds with similar mass spectra and RTs further complicate identification. Without access to reference standards, retention index databases, or spectral libraries, achieving accurate compound identification becomes even more difficult, especially in the absence of preparative chromatography and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy.

This tutorial presents seven prioritization strategies to optimize NTS workflows and to target the most relevant compounds: (P1) Target and suspect lists for matching features to curated databases; (P2) Reliability-driven prioritization which is solely based on retaining reliable data (e.g., features, components, or pixels in 2D-chromatographic data); (P3) Chemistry-driven approaches where focus is on specific compound classes or transformation patterns; (P4) Prioritization based on process-driven factors which exploits the structure in the experimental data, such as inflow-outflow comparisons; (P5) Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) and Virtual Effect-Directed Analysis (vEDA) prioritization that links features to toxicity or other endpoints; (P6) Prediction-based methods which estimate risk or concentrations of individual compounds using models; and (P7) Pixel/tile-based tools for general prioritization of chromatographic regions of interest (even before P1–P6, common in 2D data) before the detection of features or components.

For further reading, we recommend the following articles referring to different aspects of environmental NTS [2–4,7,13,15,20–23] Table 1.

Table 1

Definitions key terms used in this tutorial, which are common in NTS but often inconsistently used in literature. For further reading please refer to [13,24].

Term	Description/Definition
Feature	Single chromatographic peak in an extracted ion chromatogram (EIC), characterized by m/z , retention time (RT), and intensity
Component	Group of related features belonging to the same ion population (isotopes, adducts, multimers, or in-source fragments)
Prioritization	Process of ranking features or components to focus annotation and identification efforts on the most relevant ones
Annotation	Assigning a putative identity to a feature or component based on evidence, such as accurate mass
Identification	Confirming the putative annotation through additional evidence such as MS/MS spectra and RT
Deconvolution	Mathematical operation to resolve overlapping peaks (chromatography) or purify complex (mixture) mass spectra
Pixel	Chromatographic data point in 2D data (e.g., GC × GC) which has two RTs and spectral information associated

2. Theory

2.1. Terminology

2.2. Common steps in NTS workflows

2.2.1. Importance of high-quality raw data

The foundation of any NTS workflow is high-quality raw data. Data quality includes many different aspects starting from sampling, sample preparation and storage, suitable chromatographic and ionization conditions as well as MS parameters such as sufficient scan speed. Furthermore, data quality also refers to the generation of complete, reproducible and bias-free datasets [25,26]. Chromatography-HRMS typically generates thousands of mass spectra over a chromatographic run. This tutorial covers two main types of HRMS data: LC/SFC electrospray ionization (ESI)-HRMS and GC(× GC) electron ionization (EI)-HRMS. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the most common steps in an NTS workflow for identification of key compounds: Data acquisition (step 1), data preprocessing (step 2), prioritization (step 3) and identification (step 4).

ESI-HRMS is the standard approach for water analysis, offering soft ionization that predominately forms precursor ions (even electron ions) through adduct formation or proton abstraction. It is typically used with parallel fragmentation experiments (MS/MS). The two main acquisition strategies are data-dependent acquisition (DDA), where selected high-intensity precursor ions are fragmented, and data-independent acquisition (DIA), which fragments a broader mass range simultaneously, producing complex mixture spectra that require deconvolution for accurate identification [27].

In contrast, GC(× GC)-EI-HRMS uses hard ionization at 70 eV, generating consistent fragmentation spectra that contain both fragment ions and, in most cases, odd electron molecular ions [28]. While Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FT-ICR-MS) is also applied for NTS in complex environmental matrices, it is more difficult to integrate with chromatography (e.g., slow scan speed) and it often does not provide MS²-data [29]. Due to the strong differences in NTS data evaluation approaches compared to chromatography-HRMS, FT-ICR-MS applications are not within the scope of this tutorial.

2.2.2. Preprocessing in NTS

NTS preprocessing must be adapted to the data type (e.g., DDA vs. DIA, LC/SFC- vs. GC–HRMS) and instrument-specific variations (Preprocessing, Fig. 1). Efficient algorithms are essential to process large datasets, enabling data reduction, feature detection, and deconvolution (a mathematical way to resolve peaks). Processed signals are then structured into tabular formats for prioritization, statistical analysis, and

Fig. 1. Overview of common steps in an NTS workflow using chromatography-HRMS data. The prioritization approaches covered in this tutorial are highlighted in green and underlined. Several of these approaches are applicable to both 1D and 2D chromatographic data. Abbreviations: HRMS: high-resolution mass spectrometry, ID: identification, ROI: regions-of-interest, EDA: Effect-Directed analysis.

compound identification.

Robust preprocessing is essential for any analytical workflow and remains an active research area [24]. It typically begins with raw data conversion, followed by optional centroiding to reduce data size (Fig. 1). Next, *Regions of Interest* (ROI) are identified in the *m/z*-RT space as zones where chemical signals are expected [30,31]. Alternatively, pixel-based approaches—originally developed for 1D chromatography [32,33]—can be applied directly to pixels and have been extended to 2D chromatographic data [34,35].

Preprocessing workflows mostly follow two main approaches: stepwise processing and curve resolution techniques, with recent advancements incorporating machine learning for improved efficiency and accuracy [36].

1. Stepwise processing

Stepwise processing is widely used and implemented in many open-source tools [31,37,38]. It focuses on extracting features, grouping them into components (e.g., isotopes or adducts), and consistently recognizing them across samples. Common algorithms can be found in Renner et al. 2023 [24]. It should be noted that differences between algorithms often result in partial feature overlap and unique detections due to variations in architecture and adjustable parameters [39]. To address this, parameter optimization or validation with known standards are advisable [40–42].

The main challenge lies in achieving reliable feature detection by both reducing false negatives (ensuring all analyte features are

detected) and reducing false positives by distinguishing true analyte features from noise, particularly for low-intensity signals. In larger datasets, gap-filling can help recover missing features that may not have been detected in every sample, improving data completeness and consistency [43,44].

2. Curve resolution techniques

Curve resolution methods exploit the higher dimensionality of data to isolate signals with correlated behavior across RT and *m/z*, and sometimes across samples. These methods extract entire components—representing chemical compounds—by assuming that dataset variance arises from a finite number of sources. Unlike stepwise processing, curve resolution minimizes errors from feature grouping, where RT and *m/z* shifts can split features into multiple groups.

Common methods like multivariate curve resolution (MCR) [45] and nonnegative parallel factor analysis 2 (PARAFAC2) [27,46] are effective in resolving overlapping signals but require more computational resources than feature detection. Moreover, selecting the number of model components often requires manual input, slowing down the workflow, while with GC-MS data automatic selection of metaparameters is more suitable [46,47]. These methods also rely on assumptions such as signal linearity and additivity, which may limit their applicability.

A wide range of tools and platforms are available for NTS preprocessing, including feature detection and componentization [48]. These range from standalone software with graphical user interfaces (GUIs) to programming languages (R, Python, Julia), command-line tools, online platforms, and workflow builders such as KNIME. Examples include MZmine [49], OpenMS [50], MSDial [51], XCMS [52], patRoos [53], InSpectra [54], jHRMSToolBox [55], OpenChrom [56], PARADISE [47], and AMDIS [57].

Many of these algorithms were initially developed for metabolomics, making their default settings less suitable for environmental NTS [13, 53]. Environmental samples can be more diverse, often containing halogenated or high heteroatom count compounds, and may even include inorganic substances such as persistent and mobile compounds [10]. Therefore, it is highly important to validate workflows using known standards.

Successful preprocessing produces a table of grouped features or components, possibly including fragmentation information as well. This table serves as the starting point for prioritization strategies, which are key to successful compound identification, which will be discussed in this tutorial.

2.3. Prioritization strategies

In Table 2, the seven prioritization strategies discussed in this tutorial are briefly summarized while details, examples and further literature are provided in the “Tutorials and examples” section.

3. Tutorial and examples

3.1. Prioritization using target and suspect lists (P1)

In NTS, starting with an extensive list of potential compounds and retaining only those matching entries in specific, sample-relevant databases is an efficient prioritization strategy [58]. PubChemLite, a curated subset of PubChem, exemplifies this approach by focusing on environmentally relevant chemicals, narrowing candidates to those likely encountered in environmental contexts [58–60]. Similarly, expert-curated suspect lists, such as those from the NORMAN Suspect List Exchange and CompTox Dashboard [61–63], are valuable tools for identifying known chemicals in specific matrices. It should be noted, however, that they usually do not contain mass spectral information, making the use of further tools for confirmation necessary (e.g., in-silico

Table 2

Overview of the seven prioritization strategies discussed in this tutorial. See also Fig 1.

Method	Description
P1: Target and Suspect Lists	Compounds are prioritized using predefined lists (e.g., from NORMAN, PubChem or CompTox) or custom libraries. Detected features are matched based on accurate mass and refined with isotope patterns, MS/MS fragmentation, experimental evidence, RT, or collision-cross section (CCS). In-silico tools like MetFrag, CFM-ID, and SIRIUS+CSI: FingerID aid identification.
P2: Reliability-driven	Prioritizes data based on reliability using replicates, blanks (e.g., artifacts), and intensity corrections (e.g., matrix effects) to ensure high analytical reliability and minimize false positives and negatives. Replicate filtering balances sensitivity and specificity, blank filtering excludes artifacts, and intensity corrections account for instrument drift and/or matrix effects.
P3: Chemistry-driven	Focuses on characteristics of specific compound classes or transformation products (TPs). E.g., the class of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) by their negative mass defects, homologues series, or characteristic fragmentation patterns. Or identifying TPs involving the tracking of specific mass additions or losses due to transformations like oxidations or methylations.
P4: Process-driven	Guides prioritization based on the experimental design, such as inflow and outflow comparisons or time-series data. Identifying features by their presence in process samples can reveal persistent compounds or novel chemicals (e.g., pre- and postprocess comparison). Correlations with factors like removal efficiency, rain events, and time trends are also used.
P5: Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) prioritization	Based on correlation to sample properties like toxicity. Virtual Effect-Directed Analysis (vEDA) combines toxicological data with chemical fingerprints for prioritizing hazardous compounds. Correlations can be between toxicological markers and specific chemical classes.
P6: Prediction-based	Driven by risk assessments, using predicted concentrations and toxicities to estimate, e.g., risk quotients defined as Predicted Effect Concentration divided with Predicted No Effect Concentration (PEC/PNEC ratios). Predictive models estimate response factors using molecular descriptors, RTs, and mass spectra, focusing on compounds with the highest estimated environmental risk.
P7: Pixel/ Tile-based	Multivariate statistical methods prioritize regions of chromatograms based on relative coefficients in a model (e.g., PCA loadings). These approaches can be performed before feature detection and help to highlight compounds of interest in large datasets common for 2D data.

spectral prediction). For further reading, refer Schymanski et al.'s work on exploiting large chemical databases for exposomics [58].

After detection and grouping, features are matched to the relevant suspect list using precursor accurate mass (MS^1) as the initial criterion. Reliable identification of suspect compounds requires additional evidence, including isotope pattern matches, fragmentation data (MS^2), measured or predicted RTs, or collision-cross section (CCS) if ion mobility spectrometry (IMS) data is available [64]. However, in complex environmental samples, the high number of detected features and significant false positive rates necessitates MS/MS data for confirmation. High MS/MS coverage is advantageous and can be achieved through iterative DDA (e.g., AcquireX for Orbitraps) with exclusion lists, or DIA with effective deconvolution, although DIA can be limited by ion abundance as accurate deconvolution can become difficult in highly complex matrices.

Mass spectral libraries, such as MassBank [65], are commonly used for identification but often lack experimental data. In-silico tools such as

MetFrag and CFM-ID facilitate suspect screening by predicting MS/MS fragments for given chemical structures (from SMILES or InChI) to match experimental spectra. Tools such as SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID also allow de-novo molecular fingerprint calculation from MS/MS data [66–68]. These tools rank candidates by integrating large structural databases but typically require DDA spectra for calculations (e.g., for SIRIUS).

As an example, the identification of very mobile and small molecules through suspect screening presents unique challenges. Small molecules generate fewer fragment ions, complicating structural elucidation and MS/MS matching [10]. However, their exact mass corresponds to a narrower range of possible molecular formulas, allowing the use of alternative identifiers.

Fig. 2 outlines a suspect screening workflow for polar and mobile compounds. In this study, SFC and hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC) were used alongside LC to increase the retention of very polar compounds typically missed by conventional LC methods [10]. An extensive literature and database review led to the compilation of a suspect list of 1310 contaminants relevant to surface water. Applying the final workflow, 64 compounds were identified, including rarely analyzed compounds with high detection frequency showing their widespread occurrence [10]. While it can be time-consuming to generate sample-specific suspect lists, community-driven efforts have improved efficiency by making most lists accessible via centralized databases like PubChem or PubChemLite which also include CCS values [69].

Advantages

- Quickly narrows down candidates using sample-relevant databases and curated suspect lists.
- Integrates evidence (e.g., accurate mass, MS/MS, RT, CCS) for reliable identification.
- Improves accuracy through in-silico tools for candidate ranking.
- Allows better concentration estimation using predictive models based on molecular descriptors.

Limitations

- High false positive rates require extensive MS/MS coverage for confirmation.
- Limited experimental spectra in libraries restrict identification, with retention indices under-utilized in LC-MS.
- Manual verification is infeasible for large datasets, relying on automated workflows.

Requirements

- Accurate MS1 and MS/MS data for matching and confirmation.
- Access to curated suspect lists (e.g., PubChemLite, CompTox) and mass spectral libraries (e.g., MassBank).
- In-silico tools for fragment prediction and ranking, and DDA/DIA for comprehensive MS/MS coverage.

3.2. Reliability-driven prioritization (data filtering) (P2)

In NTS, data filtering and correction steps are critical for prioritizing reliable features while minimizing false positives. However, these steps must be customized to the research objective to avoid excessive false negatives. It should be noted that P2 alone does not sufficiently narrow down features for identification purposes and should therefore always be combined with further prioritization strategies.

3.2.1. Replicate filtering

Replicate filtering balances false negatives and positives, with strategies dependent on the study goals, resources, and user expertise. Sampling replicates are independent samples collected from the same

Fig. 2. Example of a general suspect screening workflow used for the prioritization and identification of persistent and mobile (PM) compounds which includes tailored step important to capture PM compounds (e.g., sample enrichment). Abbreviations: EC: evaporative concentration, mISPE: multi-layer solid phase extraction, S/N: signal-to-noise ratio. Reprinted from [10] with permission from Elsevier.

population, environment or setup to determine sampling variation. They are ideal for data filtering, as only features or trends detected across all replicates are retained [70]. Technical replicates, which are repeated measurements of the same sample using the same method, assess overall work-up and instrumental precision [71]. While less costly, they cannot be used to exclude features consistently detected within one sample only, but absent across sub-samples from the same population. Injection replicates are repeated injections of the same sample extract that can be used to determine the instrumental precision. These are practical to use for resource-limited studies, but the practical gain comes with a higher risk of false positives. For filtering ubiquitous pollutants, the replicate filter can be adjusted to prioritize compounds consistently detected in more than a pre-defined percentage of samples.

- **Strict filtering** (e.g., requiring a feature to occur in all three replicates with low intensity variation) minimizes false positives, ensuring high consistency, creates a “clean” dataset ideal for sharing with less experienced users. This approach reduces the risk of misinterpreting false positives as significant findings and is especially useful in mechanistic studies, such as understanding the removal or transformation of specific compounds, where consistency across replicates (preferably sampling replicates) improves reliability.
- **Less strict filtering** (e.g., for a feature to occur in two of three replicates with higher intensity variation) allows greater flexibility for broad

screenings, accommodating minor inconsistencies like peak-picking errors. However, it increases the risk of false positives and demands more curation in later stages.

Filtering should go beyond occurrence thresholds to avoid missing low-abundance features as many features even if above the threshold will be unreliable. One method is to use relative standard deviation (e.g., retaining features with <30 % RSD in method replicates) as an extraction filtering step as it will ensure greater reliability of the retained features. Features can also be selected based on diagnostic power, retaining only those with high variance between samples compared to variance in replicates or quality controls (QCs) [72].

3.2.2. Blank filtering

Blank filtering in NTS prevents misattribution of blank- or instrument-derived features to environmental samples. For robust filtering, we recommend at least three laboratory or field blanks. Many strategies use average peak intensity fold change as a threshold [51,53], but a stricter approach uses the maximum blank intensity as a cut-off [73]. Caution is needed near detection limits, where gap filling can overestimate blank values and lead to overfiltering. Compounds, such as phthalates and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) that are frequent instrument contamination, require careful evaluation to distinguish features with consistent, higher occurrences in samples from

those in blanks, even when fold-change thresholds are exceeded.

3.2.3. Intensity drift and matrix effect correction

To ensure sample comparability, intensity correction mitigates drift and matrix effects. Gradual contamination of the ion source can cause intensity drift, affecting statistical analysis. This can be minimized by randomizing replicates within the sequence and grouping related samples (e.g., wastewater influent and effluent) together. Drift correction relies on QCs, such as pooled samples [74] and surrogate internal standards where the latter further addresses injection-level variability and matrix effects [75].

Matrix effects hinder reliable feature comparison, causing signal suppression in LC-ESI [76] caused by ion competition in the electrospray or signal enhancement in GC [77,78] from matrix coverage of active sites in the liner and column. Correction is difficult because surrogate internal standards are unavailable for most NTS features, many of which remain unidentified. Effective strategies include:

- Comparing total ion chromatograms (TICs) of samples and blanks to estimate matrix effects (e.g., ion competition effects in LC-ESI [79]).
- Selecting internal standards which result in the lowest relative standard deviation (RSD) across a QC dilution series [75].
- Diluting samples to reduce matrix effects, though this bares the risk of losing low-intensity features [76].

- Appropriate sample preparation strategies such as solid-phase extraction (SPE) can further reduce matrix effects.

3.2.4. Quality control

QC should be integrated throughout data processing and during final validation of filtering steps. QC samples can include pooled or individual samples, spiked or unspiked with target compounds relevant to the samples, or standard solutions containing these targets. These QCs are important for monitoring raw data quality, and each preprocessing step through to final compound detection and identification. They should be included in the sequence and actively used during runs and for post-run workflow validation. If target compounds are unavailable, isotopically labeled (e.g., ^{13}C or D -labeled) or surrogate standards with similar structures and physicochemical properties can be used.

QC sets of high analysis frequency can be used to do intensity drift correction, while a second independent QC set can be used to validate the correction and to verify accurate componentization (e.g., correct grouping of isotopes, in-source fragments, adducts) and detection of compound splitting, where a single compound appears as multiple ungrouped features. Target compounds can also be used to assess dataset completeness by comparison with known literature. For instance, sucralose, typically resistant to removal in wastewater treatment [80], should show similar peak intensities in both influent and effluent samples, confirming the reliability of data preprocessing. An example of a complete reliability-driven prioritization workflow is provided in Fig. 3

Fig. 3. Workflow example for identification of micropollutants in wastewater, illustrating key steps in data preprocessing, feature prioritization, and identification. Adapted and reprinted with permission from [81]. Abbreviations: QC: quality control, SQC: super quality control, SPE: solid-phase extraction, TIC: total ion chromatogram, WWTPs: wastewater treatment plants.

(more details in [81]).

3.2.5. Filtering by peak and raw data quality

Data quality filtering, mainly based on chromatographic peak shape, helps remove low-quality features. Detection algorithms can produce many false positives (e.g., noise identified as features), even after parameter optimization. Expert evaluation is often required to eliminate unreliable features, a time-consuming task that can delay the process if tentative identifications are discarded later. Different methods have been developed to address this, such as calculating peak quality metrics which include different metrics such as Gaussian similarity or a zigzag index [82] and using machine learning models including deep learning to classify features as true peak, false, or requiring manual verification [83–86]. Since feature quality in HRMS varies widely, these tools can be retrained with custom data sets (e.g., classified EICs).

A recent NTS preprocessing workflow introduces a data quality scoring system, tracking criteria from centroiding [87], through EIC building [88] and feature detection [89]. This score supports the prioritization of high-quality features throughout the whole preprocessing workflow. It should be noted that these approaches must be carefully validated to avoid the erroneous removal of relevant features, depending on the objectives of the NTS analysis.

Advantages

- Impose a filtering of reliable features, minimizing false positives.
- Balances strict and flexible filtering strategies to match study objectives, supporting both high-throughput and resource-limited studies.
- Incorporates intensity drift and matrix effect corrections to improve data comparability.

Limitations

- Reliability-driven prioritization is an integral part of NTS workflows; however, it should always be combined with further prioritization strategies since it cannot sufficiently narrow down features for identification.
- Strict filtering may exclude low-abundance features, increasing false negatives rates.
- Overly conservative blank filtering and matrix effect corrections can cause feature loss near detection thresholds.
- Limited availability of surrogate internal standards for NTS features reduce the accuracy of intensity drift and matrix effect corrections, weakening data comparability across large sample sets.

Requirements

- Sufficient sampling, technical, and injection replicates, along with system and field blanks, to ensure consistent and reliable filtering.
- Access to QCs, including stabilized pooled samples (e.g., frozen water extracts, soil, biota) and target compound mixtures for workflow validation. Multiple QC sets are required per sequence: One extensively analyzed in one or more dilutions, for drift and matrix effect corrections, and additional sets for validation.
- Tools for filtering unreliable features, drift correcting using pooled QCs and standards, and efficient matrix effect correction.

3.3. Chemistry-driven prioritization (P3)

HRMS data allows the prioritization of specific compound classes based on chemical characteristics and intrinsic data properties. Filtering criteria include unique compound properties and MS^1/MS^2 data features such as accurate mass, isotope patterns, chemical mass defect (MD), RT, and fragmentation data. Compound classes commonly prioritized include PFAS, halogenated compounds (e.g., polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), flame retardants, disinfection byproducts (DBPs), dioxins),

surfactants, polymeric compounds, and TPs. Generic approaches like molecular networking can also be applied without restriction to a specific compound class.

3.3.1. Mass defect and homologues series

The chemical mass defect (MD) is the difference between a compound's accurate and nominal mass ($MD = m/z_{\text{accurate}} - m/z_{\text{nominal}}$) [90]. It reflects elemental composition; for example, PFAS usually have a negative to slightly positive MD (−0.2 to 0.05) due to high fluorine content ($MD_F = -0.0016$), while hydrogen-dominated organic molecules have a higher MD ($MD_H = +0.0078$) (Fig. 4). Since carbon has a MD of zero per definition ($C = 12.0000$), deviations arise only from other elements, especially strong MD changes are caused by elements such as bromine and iodine. MD filtering is designed for specific compound classes, simplifies mass spectra, aids manual interpretation (e.g., detecting MD shifts from characteristic losses), and helps to prioritize features based on their MD [91–93].

Both anthropogenic and natural compounds often occur as complex mixtures with repeating chemical units (e.g., CH_2 , CH_2O , CF_2 , O), resulting from chemical synthesis (e.g., surfactants, PFAS), natural processes (e.g., hydrocarbons in mineral oils), or transformations (e.g., chemical oxidation). An extension of the MD is the Kendrick mass defect (KMD) which normalizes masses to a defined repeating unit, aligning homologous series to a consistent KMD within mass uncertainty [94]. This method is widely used to detect PFAS [95], surfactants [96], hydrocarbons [97], halogenated compounds [98], and has specific applications for TPs, such as N-oxides formed during wastewater ozonation [99]. An example of a CF_2 -based KMD vs. m/z plot for PFAS prioritization is shown in Fig. 5.

To improve reliability in complex samples, RT data is incorporated, as homologous series often show consistent RT patterns (e.g., increasing RT with chain length in reversed phase-LC). Furthermore, searching for mass differences to detect compounds with elemental mass differences of interest (e.g., +O for an oxidation that forms different TPs) can also be applied without the use of the KMD.

3.3.2. Isotope patterns

Anthropogenic compounds that contain certain elements such as halogens often have distinct isotope patterns, distinguishing them from natural compounds in MS^1 data. Halogenated CECs, including organochlorine pesticides, brominated flame retardants, PFAS, and PCBs, are of environmental concern due to their persistence and bioaccumulation potential [100]. Compounds that contain sulfur or metals can also be identified based on characteristic isotope patterns.

Chlorine and bromine produce distinctive isotope patterns detectable in MS^1 data and through automated detection [101]. In contrast, elements with a single isotope, such as fluorine and iodine, require alternative prioritization approaches such as a recently proposed method for prioritization of PFAS and other heteroatom-rich compounds that uses carbon-normalized mass (m/C) and mass defect (MD/C) [102, 103]. The carbon number of features can be estimated from the ratio of

Fig. 4. Chemical MD of typical elements in typical CECs. The MD is especially useful for CECs with a high halogen content (or elements such as S and P), mostly exhibit distinct MDs compared to natural compounds.

Fig. 5. CF_2 -based PFAS homologues series detected in a contaminated soil extract measured by LC–HRMS [95]. Colored dots represent assigned features, while grey dots are unassigned features.

the intensity of the monoisotopic $[M]$ and the $[M + 1]$ isotopic peak. Many PFAS have higher m/C ratios due to their high fluorine content, enabling clear separation from common organic compounds. Fig. 6a illustrates an MD/C vs. m/C plot.

This approach also holds potential to prioritize other heteroatomic compounds, such as iodinated compounds and polyphosphates. Due to the strong focus on PFAS, specific open-source tools have been developed to automate their prioritization by integrating several prioritization strategies [104,105].

3.3.3. Common functionalities of interest

MS/MS fragmentation is widely used to prioritize compounds with specific functional groups by detecting diagnostic fragments or neutral losses [108,109]. This can be achieved through fragmentation strategies such as DDA, DIA, in-source fragmentation, or EI. Characteristic fragments or neutral losses (e.g., I for iodinated compounds, CO_2 loss for carboxylic acids, or $\text{C}_n\text{F}_{2n-1}$ for PFAS) link fragments to their precursors [110,111].

For example, detecting target fragments in MS/MS spectra allows prioritization of MS^1 features within the corresponding RT region, particularly when DDA precursors are known. This approach has been used effectively to identify PFAS across different matrices using DIA, in-source fragmentation and DDA [110,112–115].

3.3.4. Spectral similarity and molecular networking

Identified compounds or known targets can guide the prioritization

of structurally related compounds (e.g., TPs) by searching for features with high MS/MS spectral similarity. Compounds sharing fragment ions are often structurally related, with metrics like cosine similarity commonly used for evaluation [116]. Molecular networking like GNPS, enables the detection of related compounds across large datasets and is widely applied in metabolomics and environmental NTS [117]. However, this method requires clean MS/MS spectra with multiple diagnostic fragments, limiting its use mainly to DDA data. Molecular networking has been successfully used to identify TPs in wastewater and riverbank filtration studies [118,119].

3.3.5. Collision cross section (ion mobility spectrometry)

Ion-mobility spectrometry (IMS) is increasingly used in environmental NTS as an additional separation dimension due to improved identification confidence, reduction of interferences, and improved signal-to-noise ratios, and increasing spectral purity in DIA [120–122]. IMS enables direct comparison with experimental and predicted CCS databases, such as AllCCS [123]. CCS values, which describe analyte separation in the gas phase based on size, shape, and charge, can be applied to classify and prioritize compound classes. Halogenated compounds, for example, often have reduced CCS values compared to non-halogenated substances of similar mass, aiding prioritization through CCS vs. m/z plots (see Fig. 6b) [124–126].

Advantages

- Targets specific compound classes (e.g., PFAS, halogenated compounds) based on chemical properties.
- Clusters structurally related compounds using MD, homologous series, and isotope patterns, improving identification reliability.
- Supports diverse applications with tools like molecular networking for detecting structurally related compounds.

Limitations

- Relies on prior knowledge of diagnostic fragments, neutral losses, or chemical properties.
- Limited by fragmentation coverage and reliance on DDA data for molecular networking.
- Complex datasets may produce false positives, requiring further validation.

Requirements

Fig. 6. (a) MD/C vs. m/C plot of features detected in PFAS-contaminated soil (LC–HRMS). PFAS, dominated by fluorine, have distinctly higher m/C ratios compared to organic compounds (OCs) dominated by CH, enabling efficient prioritization. Reprinted with permission from [106]. Copyright 2024 American Chemical Society. (b) CCS vs. m/z plot illustrating the prioritization of halogenated compound classes in the presence of biomolecules using IMS-dimension. Reprinted from [107]. Copyright 2024 American Chemical Society.

- Unique compound properties to ensure clear differentiation from other detected features
- Integration of predicted RT and CCS measures to improve accuracy and minimize false positives.

3.4. Process- and source-driven prioritization (P4)

Feature prioritization in NTS is important for identifying CECs, understanding transformation processes, and refining environmental assessments. A process- and source-driven prioritization strategy uses knowledge of how contaminants are formed, transported, and introduced into environmental systems. This approach integrates three strategies:

- Process-Based Prioritization – Focuses on identifying contaminants formed, removed, or transformed during environmental and engineered processes, such as wastewater or drinking water treatment.
- Correlation- and Event-Based Prioritization – Uses statistical correlations to identify compounds originating from common sources or linked to specific environmental events, such as rainfall or seasonal variations.
- Source-Defined Prioritization – Targets known chemical signatures from specific sources, such as plant-derived toxins or industrial discharges, to track their presence in environmental samples.

3.4.1. Process understanding

Understanding the fate of chemicals in engineered and environmental processes is key to assessing contaminant persistence and transformation. Many organic compounds undergo structural modifications during treatment, forming TPs with unknown toxicological and environmental relevance [127,128]. Identifying and prioritizing these TPs in NTS is important for evaluating treatment efficiency and potential downstream risks.

For example, in drinking water treatment, a structured prioritization approach can track the formation of TPs by comparing influent and effluent profiles. As shown in Fig. 7, a robust workflow was applied to

detect newly formed compounds by excluding those present in all influent samples and selecting only those appearing in at least two of nine effluent samples. This approach reduces false positives by excluding compounds detected sporadically, i.e. of single occurrence and focuses on compounds that persist through treatment. Similarly, prioritization in biological activated carbon (BAC) filtration requires filtering compounds based on consistent trends, only retaining those that remain stable or follow a logical removal pattern (Fig. 7, BAC 1–4). For example, a compound detected in BAC effluents 1 and 4 but falling below the intensity threshold in effluents 2 and 3, was excluded. This stepwise filtering reduced the number of prioritized TPs by 7 %, with increased focus on compounds that persist into drinking water resources.

Beyond drinking water treatment, process-based prioritization is relevant in municipal wastewater treatment, industrial effluent monitoring, and environmental degradation studies. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) and chlorination, for instance, generate highly reactive intermediates, some of which form stable TPs that persist in distribution systems. In such cases, prioritization efforts should consider:

- Parent-compound degradation: Prioritizing features that significantly decrease in abundance, suggesting transformation.
- Formation of new peaks: Identifying newly formed compounds in effluents that were absent in influents.
- Persistence trends: Tracking contaminants through multiple treatment stages to assess removal efficiency.

Correcting for variability in influent and effluent matrices is crucial in process-based prioritization [79]. The complexity of wastewater and drinking water matrices can introduce biases, making advanced normalization and background correction strategies necessary to obtain comparable results. By integrating hierarchical clustering and trend-based filtering (Fig. 8) process-based prioritization provides a strategy framework for identifying chemical trends and transformation pathways in complex treatment systems.

This strategy can also be used to compare seasonal variations and sampling origins, providing insight into temporal trends and source-

Fig. 7. Heatmap showing 128 influent compounds and 206 transformation products (TPs) analyzed via LC–HRMS to prioritize stable compounds and those formed during drinking water treatment processes. Reprinted with permission from [127] (see there for further details).

Fig. 8. Correlation matrix of micropollutants in effluent samples, highlighting distinct clusters. Micropollutant concentrations are range-scaled (0 = lowest, 1 = highest) and hierarchically clustered using Euclidean distance. Black boxes indicate significant clusters based on shared temporal and source-based correlations. The color gradient represents Pearson correlation coefficients (calculated with MetaboAnalyst [136]), with red indicating strong positive correlations (1.0) and yellow indicating strong negative correlations (−1.0). This clustering approach reveals patterns in micropollutant behavior and potential common sources in WWTP effluents. Reprinted (adapted) with permission from [131]. Copyright 2025 American Chemical Society. Abbreviations: CECs: contaminants of emerging concern.

specific fingerprints. For example, hierarchical cluster analysis of differential features has successfully identified distinct seasonal patterns in pollutant composition, illustrating the broad applicability of this prioritization approach [129].

3.4.2. Correlation- and event-based prioritization

Correlation-based prioritization is a powerful approach in NTS that identifies contaminants based on statistical relationships, spatial patterns, and environmental events. By analyzing co-occurrence trends and fluctuations in response to external drivers, this method refines feature selection and improves the identification of pollution sources and provides an opportunity to guide regulatory bodies and agencies to act on major polluters [130,131].

A key application is the detection of contaminants that frequently co-occur due to common origins. Kilpinen et al. (2024) used hierarchical clustering to classify micropollutants in wastewater effluents by grouping samples and correlating intensity profiles of the same compounds across samples [130,131]. Industrial discharges showed distinct clustering patterns, with spikes in pharmaceutical and industrial chemical concentrations suggesting episodic pollution events. This approach also revealed variations in treatment efficiency, highlighting contaminants that were insufficiently removed under changes in operational conditions (reducing the residence time in the WWTP). External

factors such as rainfall, seasonal variations, and fluctuations in wastewater treatment performance can significantly impact contaminant behavior, requiring event-driven prioritization. Kilpinen et al. (2024) found that hydraulic variability in wastewater treatment plants affected pharmaceutical removal, with elevated effluent concentrations during peak flow conditions when treatment efficiency declined. This approach prioritized compounds that were consistently less removed under variable treatment loads, identifying those most likely to persist in receiving waters. An example of a correlation heatmap used for correlation and event-based prioritization is provided in Fig. 8 [132].

Albergamo et al. (2019) applied a similar clustering approach to analyze micropollutant behavior in riverbank filtration systems [133]. By tracking contaminant persistence across multiple sampling locations, they distinguished historical contamination from newly introduced pollutants. The study found that some persistent polar micropollutants, such as carbamazepine and sulfamethoxazole, were only partially removed by bank filtration, leading to their continued detection in downstream drinking water supplies. The prioritization of these compounds was guided by their consistent occurrence and resistance to natural attenuation processes.

Spatially distributed sampling further strengthens prioritization by tracking how contaminant profiles change spatially. Davila-Santiago et al. (2022) investigated a creek receiving multiple pollution inputs,

linking specific pollutants to an upstream wastewater treatment plant [134]. Their approach relied on chemical profiles, identifying pharmaceuticals, artificial sweeteners, and industrial chemicals that were consistently detected downstream but absent in upstream locations. This study also demonstrates the importance of spatially resolved data in distinguishing pollution sources and prioritizing site-specific contaminants.

Rain events are another key driver of contaminant fluctuations. Hopke (2003) and other studies have shown that stormwater runoff frequently introduces high loads of PFAS, tire-wear chemicals, pesticides, and heavy metals into surface waters [135]. The episodic nature of these contamination spikes makes traditional monitoring strategies inadequate for detecting short-lived pollution events. By prioritizing contaminants that consistently appear following rain events, it is possible to target sampling efforts and improve the detection of event-driven pollution sources.

Overall, correlation- and event-based prioritization improves environmental monitoring by integrating statistical clustering, spatial tracking, and dynamic event analysis. These approaches provide critical insights into pollutant behavior, allowing for the identification of contaminants that persist, fluctuate, or originate from distinct sources. However, their effectiveness depends on high-quality datasets, robust statistical models, and careful interpretation of confounding factors such as bioactivity-driven degradation and variability in pollution sources.

3.4.3. Source-supported prioritization

Source-supported prioritization targets contaminants originating from known sources, such as industrial discharges, plant-derived toxins, or synthetic chemicals. This approach resembles suspect-list strategies but uniquely relies on direct chemical analysis of the original source to guide targeted screening downstream. By characterizing source-specific compounds first, their chemical signature can be efficiently traced in environmental compartments. A key approach involves extracting and analyzing source-specific compounds before screening environmental samples. Liang et al. (2021) applied this method by extracting phytochemicals from cropped lupin, enabling the prioritization and identification of 72 plant-derived contaminants in agricultural soil, drainage water, and surface water (Fig. 9) [137]. By matching peaks in environmental samples to the chemical profile of lupin extracts, this approach refined contaminant selection and improved identification confidence. The workflow for this strategy is illustrated in Fig. 9, where chemical profiling of a known source (e.g., plant material) is used to screen environmental matrices. Identified peaks in the source extract are compared with those in soil, drainage water, and surface water, enabling targeted prioritization and identification of relevant contaminants.

However, source attribution is often complicated by bioactivity-induced degradation, where microbial activity or environmental processes modify contaminant structures before detection.

Advantages

- Integrates spatial/temporal data with sample correlations to improve source identification and trend analysis.
- Adaptable for multiple applications including source apportionment, source tracking, and treatment process assessment.
- Adds to regulatory decision-making by linking contaminants to specific sources and identifying pollutants of specific interest.

Limitations

- Requires use of advanced statistical methods, increasing analytical complexity and computational demands.
- Relies on high-quality data from targeted spatial and temporal sampling; inconsistencies in influent and effluent matrices can introduce bias if not properly corrected.
- External factors such as rainfall and bioactivity-induced degradation can obscure contaminant trends, complicating source attribution and prioritization efforts.

Requirements

- Robust workflows to filter false positives, manage temporal variability, and ensure reliable data trend detection.
- Extensive sampling at multiple locations and time points to improve pattern recognition and event-driven prioritization.
- Bias correction tools and normalization techniques to account for matrix variability in e.g., influent and effluent wastewater samples.

3.5. Effect-directed analysis (EDA) prioritization (P5)

EDA prioritization uses biological effects such as eco-toxicity or mutagenicity, to guide contaminant identification. Two established methods in environmental science, traditional EDA and Virtual Effect-Directed Analysis (vEDA), apply bioactivity-based selection but differ in workflow and applications.

EDA is a multi-step approach that combines biological assays, fractionation, and chemical analysis to identify toxicants in environmental samples [138,139]. The workflow involves:

- Sample Preparation: Collection and processing of environmental samples (e.g., water, sediment).

Fig. 9. The diagram illustrates how chemical profiling of a source is used to identify its chemical footprint in environmental compartments. Peaks detected in the source extract are compared to those in soil, drainage water, and surface water, enabling a more targeted and efficient prioritization process. Reprinted from [137]. Copyright 2023 American Chemical Society.

- Fractionation: Separation of the sample into fractions to reduce complexity.
- Biological Assays: Screening fractions for toxic effects using biological assays.
- Chemical Analysis: identifying the responsible toxicants using analytical separation techniques such as LC–HRMS and GC–HRMS.

Fractionation reduces sample complexity, allowing comparisons between bioactive and non-bioactive fractions to guide prioritization. However, the process is labor-intensive and time-consuming and does not always guarantee reduced complexity, as toxicants with similar chemical properties may elute together which can undermine the efficiency of the workflow for large-scale applications.

EDA was demonstrated by Lopez-Herguedas et al. [140], who used sea urchin embryo bioassays to assess toxicity in hospital effluent. Following a two-step fractionation using C_{18} and aminopropyl semi-preparative columns, the samples were analyzed with LC–HRMS and GC–MS to detect a broad range of chemicals. This workflow reduced an initial pool of >446 unidentified features to 94 potential toxicants, of which 25 compounds were confirmed using chemical standards (Fig. 10).

EDA has also been successfully applied to identify previously unknown toxicants. For instance, Tian et al. (2021) identified the tire-derived contaminant 6PPD-quinone as the cause of acute mortality in coho salmon, showing the ability of EDA to detect ecologically relevant toxicants within complex environmental samples [141]. Further, Neale et al. (2023) emphasized that EDA complements targeted and non-targeted analyses by addressing cumulative biological impacts of chemical mixtures, making it valuable for regulatory monitoring and water quality management [142].

While EDA is effective in identifying toxicants, its reliance on physical fractionation limits its scalability, making it less practical for large-scale environmental studies. vEDA emerges as a complementary data-driven approach that identifies bioactive compounds using multivariate statistics and pattern recognition without physical fractionation [143]. vEDA integrates HRMS data with statistical modeling to correlate chemical features with biological effects, prioritizing compounds potential causative agents for the effects [144].

Key aspects of vEDA are:

- Incorporation of target, suspect, and NTS to assess known and unknown chemicals.

- Statistical modeling (e.g., partial least squares (PLS) regression) to link chemical occurrence with observed bioactivity.
- Identification of candidate toxicants based on statistical significance, followed by validation through chemical databases, toxicological models, or experimental testing.
- Scalability, as it enables analysis across hundreds of samples without requiring fractionation.

One advantage of vEDA is its ability to prioritize toxicants even when toxicity arises from complex mixtures containing dozens or hundreds of chemicals. In a typical vEDA workflow, features or compounds are used as a basis for multivariate analysis [143,145–147]. These methods maximize the covariance between predictor variables (X) (features) and response variables (Y) (biological effects) [148].

Multivariate techniques such as PLS provide intrinsic importance metrics that highlight the most relevant features (contained in X) for prioritization according to the response variables (contained in Y). Examples include regression coefficients – indicating the contribution of each variable to the response, Selectivity Ratios (SR) – assessing the strength of the relationship between a feature and the biological effect, and Variable Importance in Projection (VIP) scores – ranking features based on their influence on model predictability [149–151]. These metrics, alone or combined with variable selection techniques (e.g., sparse methods, genetic algorithms, or interval PLS [152–155]), serve as valuable tools in the prioritization step, that enables to focus on features that most significantly contribute to the observed toxicity [156].

Hug et al. [146] demonstrated vEDA to identify mutagenic micropollutants in wastewater. LC–HRMS/MS data were processed into features, and a PLS regression model linked detected peaks to bioactivity measured using the Ames Fluctuation Test (AFT). PLS analysis combined with Iterative variable selection progressively eliminated peaks with low importance, narrowing the focus to four toxic micropollutants: The newly identified 4-(dimethylamino)-pyridine, and three known micropollutants: benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid, phenylbenzimidazole sulfonic acid, and diclofenac. These findings highlight the potential of vEDA to prioritize biologically relevant compounds in complex environmental samples.

Advantages

- Prioritizes chemical features directly associated with toxicological endpoints, ensuring relevance to specific biological questions.
- vEDA eliminates the need for physical fractionation.

Fig. 10. Workflow of EDA with orthogonal fractionation. SPE, sea urchin embryo test (SET) bioassay, blank samples (B). For the first fractionation: fractions (F1–18), raw sample (RAW), recombined sample (RS), pool of the three active fractions (ΣF); for the second fractionation: fractions ($\Sigma F-1-16$) and recombined sample ($\Sigma F-RS$). Reprinted with permission from [140].

- Well-suited for analyzing complex mixtures with potentially hundreds of contributing toxicants, offering scalability for large datasets.

Limitations

- Requires consistently and reliably measured biological responses in samples; inadequate or noisy data can negatively affect the reliability of the prioritization.
- The choice of the biological endpoint is pivotal; an unsuitable response measure can undermine the entire prioritization process.
- vEDA relies on large datasets (hundreds to thousands of samples) and demands advanced statistical expertise for accurate implementation.

Requirements

- Biological effects and chemical occurrence patterns must show sufficient variability between samples to exceed measurement uncertainty.
- vEDA requires datasets with many samples to detect meaningful trends and correlations, with greater variance between samples necessitating even larger datasets to pinpoint key toxicants.
- High-quality NTS data and well-controlled biological response measurements are essential for reliable multivariate modeling and prioritization.

3.6. Prediction-based prioritization (P6)

Prediction-based prioritization evaluates hazards, concentrations, and risks for both identified and unidentified features. It combines predicted concentrations or toxicity to calculate risk quotients (PEC/PNEC ratios), based on molecular descriptors, RTs, and mass spectra—individually or in combination [157–161].

3.6.1. Concentration prediction

Compounds are often prioritized by their up- or downregulation during processes, typically assessed via peak intensity. However, estimating even relative concentrations from peak intensities is challenging, as intensity differences for compounds at identical concentrations can span several orders of magnitude [162]. A robust strategy is needed to quantify newly identified compounds without reference standards, especially for advancing NTS in risk assessment. Recent studies have shown potential in estimating concentrations of contaminants of emerging concern by correlating ionization efficiencies with molecular descriptors [157–159]. This workflow includes steps designed to reduce random and systematic errors:

- **Sample Preparation:** Differences in recovery rates can introduce substantial errors in concentration estimates (e.g., 1 % recovery leads to a 100-fold deviation).
- **Data Acquisition:** Instrument variability and inaccurate response factor calculations (e.g., relying only on protonated ions) [159].
- **Data Treatment:** Proper alignment and matrix effect corrections are necessary to obtain accurate peak intensity measurements, improving quantification of both known and unknown micropollutants.

LC—HRMS with ESI is the most widely used platform for quantifying unknowns, with atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) as an alternative for compounds with low ionization efficiency in ESI [163, 164]. GC(× GC)-EI-HRMS provide greater reproducibility due to controlled ionization conditions, reducing variability in ionization efficiency and facilitating model transfer between laboratories. However, these techniques can still be affected by matrix effects, particularly related to adsorption to active sites in liners and columns [165].

Most prediction models rely on molecular descriptors, assuming that chemical properties correlate with ionization efficiency and

concentration. QSPR models, trained on known compounds, have been effective in predicting concentrations of new compounds [166]. Machine learning further improves these predictions, particularly when structural information is available [158]. Further approaches exist, such as for example a dilution approach used for quantitative source apportionment [167].

An alternative approach bypasses the need for full structural identification by using MS² spectra to prioritize features with potentially high concentrations, refining the focus on environmentally or toxicologically relevant compounds. MS2Quant, a model trained on 1191 unique chemicals measured in 13 laboratories, uses machine learning to estimate ionization efficiencies directly from MS²-derived structural fingerprints [168]. Unlike conventional approaches that require full structural identification, MS2Quant predicts concentrations for both identified and unidentified chemicals with a comparable mean error factor. This method enables rapid quantification of emerging contaminants, supporting risk-based prioritization even when accurate chemical identification is unavailable.

3.6.2. Toxicity prediction

Advances in computational toxicology have improved the ability to predict the toxicity of individual compounds, particularly those detected in complex environmental mixtures. These methods help prioritize chemicals with high predicted risk quotients, accelerating risk assessment and prioritization in NTS. By focusing identification efforts on chemicals with the greatest potential for environmental or human health risks, they remain valuable even when compound identities are uncertain.

Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models are widely used for toxicity prediction by correlating molecular descriptors with toxicological endpoints [169–171]. Traditional QSAR models are limited to known chemical structures, but several studies have expanded their applicability by integrating analytical descriptors, such as mass spectra and retention indices, enabling toxicity predictions for unidentified compounds. Zushi et al. (2022) [172] demonstrated that QSAR models trained on these descriptors can estimate toxicity even without full structural identification. However, their accuracy depends on high-quality analytical data, and reliability decreases for chemicals outside the training set [172].

The Cramer decision tree, widely applied in Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) assessments, classifies chemicals based on structural complexity and inherent toxicity potential [173–175]. This classification facilitates the estimation of exposure thresholds deemed to pose negligible health risks. Class I includes simple compounds with low biological reactivity, Class II covers chemicals with moderate bioactivity or limited toxicity data, and Class III consists of complex, bioactive, or poorly studied substances requiring stricter evaluation. Despite its wide use, discrepancies in Cramer classification often arise due to differences in rule interpretation by *in silico* tools and expert judgment. Certain structural groups, such as heterocycles and lactones, are particularly problematic. Beta-lactones, for instance, are sometimes incorrectly assigned to Class I, despite their potential reactivity, highlighting the need for expert review [173].

Recent developments focus on prediction of toxicological properties directly from analytical data, eliminating the need for labor-intensive structural identification [160,161,176]. For instance, machine learning-based methods refine toxicity prediction by analyzing patterns in analytical data. Tools like MS2Tox [161] and ML*in vitro*Tox [160] use molecular fingerprints predicted from MS/MS fragmentation spectra (SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID) to predict toxicity endpoints, such as LC₅₀ values for aquatic organisms or cytotoxicity [68]. These models help prioritize chemicals in NTS datasets, enabling rapid evaluation of chemicals in complex mixtures. However, they face challenges such as data imbalance, the need for large training datasets, and difficulties in transferring models between chemical classes [160,161]. The MS2Tox model predicts ecotoxicological endpoints directly from HRMS MS/MS spectral

data, eliminating the need for full structural identification. Trained on datasets of known toxicity values and corresponding structural fingerprints, the model estimates toxicity for both identified and unidentified chemicals. The model has been applied to fish acute toxicity (LC_{50}) as an example (Fig. 10), but its scope extends to other ecotoxicological endpoints. Validation is performed by comparing predicted toxicity values against experimental data for known chemicals, while estimates for chemicals without experimental toxicity data remain unvalidated until empirical data becomes available. MLinvitroTox extends to over 100 cytotoxic endpoints which can be predicted from MS^2 spectra [160,176].

Toxicity prediction models rely on high-quality analytical and toxicological datasets, yet availability of such datasets for many environmental chemicals remains limited. Models also struggle with structurally novel or uncommon compounds, reducing predictive accuracy. Machine-learning-based approaches often lack interpretability, which also hinders regulatory acceptance, emphasizing the need for mechanistic insights and explainable models.

Fig. 11

Integrating toxicity predictions with exposure modeling offers a way to improve risk assessment frameworks. Expanding datasets to cover a wider range of chemical structures and toxicity profiles will improve model robustness and accuracy, as seen in initiatives like ToxCast and Tox21 [160]. Combining QSAR, machine learning, and EDA/vEDA could further improve prioritization by focusing on chemicals with the highest environmental and toxicological relevance.

Fig. 12 illustrates a quantitative risk assessment framework integrating bioactivity data with NTS data [177]. Bioactivity measures such as ToxCast AC50 are extrapolated to estimate lower-bound acceptable

concentrations using in vitro to in vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) and exposure modeling. At the same time, NTS-derived chemical responses are converted into upper-bound protective concentration estimates using quantitative modeling and recovery estimation. This dual approach enables risk prioritization by comparing these bounds, even in the presence of sizable estimation errors.

These advancements demonstrate how computational toxicology can effectively prioritize high-risk chemicals, even without full identification. By focusing on compounds with the greatest environmental or human health risks, these methods support more targeted risk management and strengthen regulatory decision-making.

Advantages

- Predicting risk quotients (PEC/PNEC ratios) by integrating concentration and toxicity models accelerate the identification of high-risk chemicals without full identification.
- Methods like MS2Tox, MLinvitroTox, and QSAR allow high-throughput screening of large datasets, accommodating both identified and unidentified compounds.
- Applicable to a broad range of chemicals using molecular descriptors, MS/MS data, and machine learning, making it adaptable for NTS analysis.

Limitations

- Accuracy depends on high-quality analytical and toxicological datasets, which are often scarce for emerging contaminants.

Fig. 11. Training and application of the MS2Tox model for predicting fish acute toxicity (LC_{50}) from HRMS MS/MS data. (A) The model is retrained using combined training, test, and validation datasets comprising known toxicity values and structural fingerprints. (B) Experimental HRMS (Orbitrap) spectra are processed with SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID to generate molecular fingerprints, which the MS2Tox model uses to predict toxicity values. (C) In the resulting plot, green points represent MS2Tox-predicted values that match experimental data; gray points indicate chemicals without available LC_{50} values; and transparent points highlight overlapping data regions. For some chemicals lacking fish LC_{50} data, structures and rat LD_{50} values are provided for reference. Reprinted with permission from [161].

Fig. 12. Toxicity assay measures (e.g., ToxCast AC50) are extrapolated to lower-bound acceptable concentrations via IVIVE and exposure modeling. Similarly, NTS instrument response is converted into upper-bound protective estimates through quantitative modeling and recovery estimation. Risk assessment is guided by comparing these bounds, where large concentrations errors are acceptable if the separation between them is sufficient. Reprinted from [177] with permission from Environment International.

- Models struggle with structurally novel or chemically diverse compounds outside their training set, reducing predictive accuracy.
- Machine learning models lack mechanistic transparency, which can limit regulatory acceptance and hinder adoption in decision-making frameworks.

Requirements

- Expanding and standardizing datasets (e.g., ToxCast, Tox21) to improve model accuracy and generalizability across diverse chemical classes.
- Reliable input data require HRMS, MS/MS, accurate mass spectral libraries, and descriptor-based tools like SIRIUS+CSI:FingerID
- Reliable risk assessment depends on integrating QSAR, machine learning, and exposure modeling.
- Models must undergo rigorous validation with experimental data to ensure accuracy and applicability across different chemical classes.

3.7. Pixel/Tile based prioritization (P7)

Multivariate techniques, including pixel-based and tile-based approaches (commonly used for 2D data) allow prioritization of retention time regions in data before peak detection and compound identification. Multivariate tools such as PCA and HCA reduce data dimensionality and highlight significant chromatographic and mass spectral regions, while univariate measures like Fisher ratio or diagnostic power (DP) can be extended to multivariate data and be used for variable scaling and prioritization. DP-based ranking calculated as $\text{RSD}_{\text{samples}}/\text{RSD}_{\text{QCs}}$ prioritizes pixels or tiles with high sample variation and low QC variability, improving analytical reliability [178].

3.7.1. Pixel-based analysis

Pixel-based methods, named after a signal processing paper on GC \times GC data [179], offer an alternative approach to conventional peak detection [32,72]. In pixel-based analysis raw intensity data are analyzed without feature detection and grouping. Applications exist for GC-FID data [72,180], LC-HRMS data [181], GC-MS and GC \times GC-FID and HRMS data [32,35,72]. Data are processed as vectorized samples, and PCA loadings can be refolded into chromatographic matrices for intuitive visualization. The advantage of pixel-based methods lies in

maintaining the original data structure, which simplifies interpretation and visualization of prioritized chromatographic regions.

Pixel-based methods require step-wise preprocessing to ensure reliable comparison of chemical fingerprints between samples, including noise reduction, chromatographic alignment, and normalization. Furbo et al. (2014) provided a tutorial demonstrating how GC \times GC data can be effectively processed using pixel-based methods, showing the importance of proper artifact removal such as chromatographic background subtraction and retention time alignment to reduce non-sample variations and improve data interpretability [35]. They emphasized that preprocessing steps such as alignment, noise removal, and scaling significantly affect subsequent multivariate analysis, thus important for revealing true chemical differences between samples [35].

The hyphenation of 1D or 2D chromatography with HRMS enables analysis of TICs, BPIs, and highly resolved EICs, facilitating pattern recognition in complex environmental samples. PCA, widely used for data reduction, captures dataset variation in a few principal components (PCs). For instance, Lübeck et al. (2020) used pixel-based analysis of GC \times GC-HRMS data to investigate variations in micropollutant composition in freshwater sediments from an urban lake in Copenhagen, Denmark. In this study, 91.3 % of the dataset variation was described in six PCs [178] (Fig. 13). Four of these PCs revealed distinct chemical differences, including elevated levels of monoterpenes (#47), sesquiterpenes (#61), and diterpenes (#39) linked to sediment depth. Fig. 13 visualizes these PCA loadings, where yellow pixels indicate higher relative abundance, and dark blue pixels represent lower abundance.

Accurate pixel-based prioritization requires chromatographic alignment and noise removal, who excluded PCs influenced by RT shifts. PC3 and PC4 were excluded from further analysis as their variation was dominated by retention time shifts that were not fully corrected during preprocessing [178]. Proper chromatographic alignment and removal of background noise and contaminants are essential to ensure that pixel-based analysis reflects true chemical differences. For a detailed discussion on how preprocessing and scaling impact pixel-based prioritization, see Furbo et al. (2014) [35].

3.7.2. Tile-based analysis

The tile-based approach, now commercialized, segments the 2D chromatogram into rectangular windows (“tiles”) and compares them on an extracted ion basis using F-ratio analysis [182]. Tile size must be

Fig. 13. Loading plots (PC1, PC2, PC5, and PC6) from samples collected at Fæstningskanalen in Utterslev Mose, Copenhagen, Denmark (FSK). Samples show distinct chemical patterns and compounds (refer to Table 2 in [178] for details). The dotted white circle shows unresolved misalignment in the second dimension. Reprinted with permission from [178].

carefully selected to balance sensitivity and specificity; overly large tiles can obscure low-intensity analytes by mixing them with contaminants, while overly small tiles may produce redundant hits and false positives.

Trinklein and Synovec (2022) examined the effects of detector saturation, RT shifts, and signal variability, recommending larger tile sizes to accommodate significant variations. They demonstrated how tiling, combined with ANOVA-based F-ratios, reduces false positives from RT shifts while identifying class-discriminating analytes. They also found that optimal tile size selection is critical to minimize errors and ensure accurate feature prioritization [183].

With proper preprocessing, multivariate prioritization helps filter relevant features before detection and componentization. It is especially useful for large sample sets with thousands of compounds, where setting intensity thresholds and feature detection criteria is difficult and error prone.

Advantages

- Pixel- and tile-based approaches analyze raw signal intensities directly and prioritize chromatographic regions before peak detection.

- Both methods can filter out noise by retaining only high-intensity or high-significance regions, improving the focus on relevant chemical differences.
- Pixel-based analysis ensures full alignment of the same compounds across all samples, eliminating the need to merge feature lists from multiple samples—alignment and comparison happen automatically during multivariate analysis.

Limitations

- Both approaches require rigorous chromatogram alignment and noise removal to prevent misclassification due to RT shifts or instrumental artifacts.
- Pixel-based analysis is susceptible to misalignment and requires well-aligned chromatograms for reliable results. However, scaling to QC samples affected by the same misalignment can mitigate this issue.
- Tile-based analysis depends on appropriate tile size selection, small tiles increase false positives, while large tiles risk missing analytes.

Requirements

- Meticulous preprocessing, including alignment and background noise removal is essential for accurate prioritization.
- Tile size optimization is critical to balance sensitivity and specificity, accounting for experimental variability and retention time shifts.
- Combining pixel- and tile-based methods with multivariate techniques improves feature prioritization in complex datasets.

4. Concluding remarks and perspectives

This tutorial presents seven prioritization strategies to improve NTS workflows, each offering distinct advantages: (1) target and suspect screening, (2) reliability-driven filtering, (3) chemistry-driven prioritization, (4) process-driven approaches, (5) EDA-driven methods, (6) prediction-based prioritization, and (7) multivariate techniques (pixel-/tile-based). These strategies should not be seen as mutually exclusive but rather as complementary tools that can be combined based on research objectives.

For instance, target and suspect screening (P1) often serves as an initial prioritization step when relevant suspect lists are available, but it can be further refined by integrating process-driven prioritization (P4) to assess temporal or treatment-related patterns. Similarly, pixel-based prioritization (P7) provides a broad, data-driven way to highlight chromatographic regions of interest before applying EDA-driven approaches (P5) to focus on toxicologically relevant compounds.

Each method has its advantages and limitations, but their integration strengthens the overall prioritization process. Prediction-based methods (P6) using machine learning and QSAR/QSPR allow for early risk assessment without requiring full identification, while EDA- and vEDA-driven approaches (P5) link chemical presence to biological effects, enabling direct toxicity-based prioritization.

Despite these advancements, key challenges remain. High-quality, standardized datasets are essential for ensuring reproducibility and comparability across studies. Computational demands can also be a barrier, particularly for machine learning and exposure modeling approaches that require large datasets and extensive processing power.

Moving forward, hybrid workflows that combine multiple prioritization strategies hold significant potential. For example, integrating prediction-based and EDA-driven methods can refine risk assessments by simultaneously considering chemical occurrence, toxicity, and exposure levels. Similarly, expanding and curating databases will improve the accuracy and applicability of predictive models. Advances in automated quality control, alignment algorithms, and real-time data preprocessing will further enhance prioritization efficiency.

Ultimately, prioritization strategies are critical for managing the complexity of chemical data in NTS. By adopting flexible and scalable workflows that integrate multiple approaches as needed, researchers can improve identification efficiency, enhance environmental risk assessment, and support more targeted regulatory decision-making. Future developments should focus on harmonizing prioritization workflow to ensure that NTS remains a powerful tool for detecting and assessing emerging contaminants.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jonathan Zweigle: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Selina Tisler:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marta Bevilacqua:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Giorgio Tomasi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nikoline J. Nielsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Nadine Gawlitta:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Josephine S. Lübeck:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Age K. Smilde:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Jan H. Christensen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the findings of this study.

Data availability

The data which is created by the authors are fully available on request.

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